

‘Base by Birth, Mean by Estate, and Calling’: Fashion and the Social Order in Early Modern England

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Abstract

Recent historiographical trends have begun to reemphasise the integral role played by dress in early modern society and its unique role in fostering both individual and group identities. However, little attention has been paid to placing these new discoveries within the broader narrative of social history. In doing so, it becomes apparent that dress is integral to the formation and conception of the early modern social order and the complex interactions between communities. This paper seeks to synthesise historiographical developments in the field of English social history as well as textile studies. This way, this study aims to demonstrate that dress in early modern England provided a unique opportunity for members of the aspirational middling sort to self-fashion in an increasingly mobile society, challenging traditional roles and leading to anxiety amongst the gentry and aristocracy. In addition, this research draws upon a diverse array of primary sources, including sermons, conduct books, and English sumptuary legislation to reveal the contemporary importance of costume and appearance. Ultimately, in consolidating these disparate sources, one can observe the crucial role fashion played in the arbitration and enforcement of the social order in early modern England, and thus, its usefulness as an analytical tool for social historians.

Introduction

It seems incongruous that clothing, an object as old and ever-changing as society itself, has seldom been incorporated into the examination of early modern lives. Scholars frequently disregard costume studies as ‘hemline histories’ practical solely for dating artwork, or at best, an economic analysis of consumption patterns.¹ Finally, historians are beginning to explore the profound impact of textiles on the complex relationships of early modern society.² As recent scholarship has noted, clothing was a means to construct and maintain individual identities and to emphasise and delineate between socio-economic hierarchies.³ Social order and the complex, interlocking relationships that governed society remains a prominent topic of discussion amongst social historians of the early modern period. Their interest reveals how the ‘middling sort’, a dynamic group existing between the landed gentry and the labouring poor, comprised of individuals ranging from yeomen farmers to urban artisans, routinely challenged this traditional order within an increasingly mobile society.⁴ The study of dress, though often ignored, provides compelling evidence to support the dramatic and radical changes observed by historians, particularly contemporary attitudes towards clothing, differences between urban and rural regions, and the institution of sumptuary legislation. Through an analysis of these historiographical strands, supplemented by an array of primary material, it is evident that while elite society attempted to use clothing as a way to enforce social stratification, ultimately these same resources set a standard of ‘fashionability’ that allowed the middling sort to more effectively emulate the gentry and demonstrate their social mobility.

¹ Christopher Breward, *The Culture of Fashion* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1995), 1-3 and S. Vincent, ‘When I am in Good Habit’: Clothes in English Culture c. 1550 - c. 1670’ (PhD diss., University of York, 2002), 12-16.

² Susan Vincent, *Dressing the Elite: Clothes in Early Modern England* (Oxford: Berg, 2003), 2.

³ Diana Crane, *Fashion and its Social Agendas: Class, Gender and Identity in Clothing* (London: University of Chicago Press, 2000), 4.

⁴ Jonathan Barry, ‘Introduction’, in *The Middling Sort of People: Culture, Society, and Politics in England, 1550-1800*, ed. John Barry et. all (London: Palgrave, 1994), 2.

This article seeks to assess the degree to which dress can be used as an analytical tool for social historians investigating the middling sort in early modern England. It will investigate how scholars have utilised dress in their studies and the conception of clothing by contemporaries through the employment of historiography on early modern clothing, trade, sumptuary legislation, and moral conduct, alongside contemporary sermons, conduct books, and acts or proclamations of apparel from the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. By marrying historiographical trends with primary source analysis, it becomes apparent that early modern society was preoccupied with clothing. It is evident that both the gentry and the middling sort conceived dress as crucial to understanding their social identity and position in the ‘great chain of being’. More specially, garments held both a moral and political importance, and it was increasingly important for members of the gentry and aristocracy to safeguard their apparel through various means. Aspirational members of the middling sort could simultaneously use dress within their socially mobile societies to emulate the gentry and blur social hierarchies. Therefore, this essay presents a guide to scholars seeking to understand the impact of fashion on the social, political, and moral makeup of early modern English society, ultimately establishing that the study of clothing and textiles has a place within the historiography of social history alongside more traditional studies.

Historiographical Roots of Fashion and the Social Order

To understand the complexity of early modern social relations and the influence of clothing on the establishment of social order, one must connect their seemingly disparate theoretical and historiographical foundations. Of note is Thorstein Veblen’s *The Theory of the Leisure Class*. Even though its focus was on late nineteenth-century American fashion, Veblen’s thesis, specifically his theories on emulation and conspicuous consumption can be directly applied to

the study of early modern communities. Clothing was carefully guarded and consumed by elite members of the male society as a display of their reputability and status as gentlemen.⁵ The fact that those with financial means, identified as the bourgeoisie or middle class by Veblen, deliberately emulated these styles through their personal consumption, prompted the need for a constant redevelopment of fashionable apparel in order to maintain distinct socio-economic group identities.⁶ Veblen's work has fundamentally influenced the way scholars have studied fashion and its influence on social order. Its distinct Marxist elements provide an inextricable connection to the study of social history and the labours of historians such as Daniel Roche, whose analysis of early modern French fashion reaches a similar conclusion, asserting that 'clothes became weapons in the battle of appearances'.⁷ Veblen's theory is reinforced through Norbert Elias's *The Civilising Process*, which outlines the nobility's attempts to create a unique culture, and a subsequent 'trickle-down' effect in which civilised behaviours travelled down the social ladder from the elite to their 'social inferiors'.⁸ In tandem, these two influential works support this essay's claim that the processes of emulation and conspicuous consumption were affecting social relations and disturbing social order in early modern England.

Furthermore, the study and contextual importance of social history are integral to understanding the complex dynamic between clothing and social relations. E.M.W Tillyard notably provides a careful analysis of Elizabethan social structures by outlining the ideas of the Great Chain of Being and the Body Politic in Elizabethan thought and writing.⁹ Analogous works also demonstrate how these imagined orders manifested, looking specifically at gestural codes and

⁵ Thorstein Veblen, *The Theory of the Leisure Class* (London, 1899), 24, 53.

⁶ Veblen, *The Theory of the Leisure Class*, 22.

⁷ D.E Allen, 'Fashion as a Social Process', *Textile History* 22 (1991): 350 and Daniel Roche, *The Culture of Clothing: Dress and Fashion in the Ancien Regime* (trans. by Jean Birrell) (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1996), 6.

⁸ Norbert Elias, *The Civilising Process* (London: Wiley-Blackwell, 2000), 64, 116.

⁹ E.M.W Tillyard, *The Elizabethan World Picture* (London, 1943).

books of conduct in the enforcement of elite identity and the maintenance of the social order, drawing heavily from the anthropological observations of Norbert Elias.¹⁰ Governed by Marxist ideology, early social historians, such as E.P. Thompson and J.H. Hexter, failed to acknowledge the importance of the middling sort in this order, in favour of ‘history from below’.¹¹ This was challenged by the social historians of the 1980s, especially by Keith Wrightson, whose work is invaluable in understanding the nature of social relations in England in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, and particularly, the role played by the middling sort in this complicated community. Wrightson highlights the ability to transition between the lower gentry and the middling sort as well as contemporary ideas of social order that demonstrate ‘society as it ought to be’ in contrast to reality.¹² Wrightson’s work led to a growing interest in studying the middling sort, encapsulated most comprehensively in the collected essays *The Middling Sort of People* edited by Jonathan Barry and Christopher Brooks.¹³ These studies parallelly describe the principal strains of social history that come together to illuminate scholars on the complex web of social relationships in early modern England and provide a frame of reference for this essay. More specifically, these sources provide a conceptual framework as to who, exactly, constituted the middling sort in early modern England and how they could interact with members of the gentry within their local communities. It also illuminates the blurring social boundaries within early modern society, which allowed the middling sort to utilise dress as a form of social currency and provide insight into the role of morality and religion in contemporary society.

¹⁰ See, for example, J. Walter, ‘Gesturing at Authority: Deciphering the Gestural Code of Early Modern England’, in, *The Politics of Gesture: Historical Perspectives*, ed. M Braddick (Past and Present, Supplement, 4, 2009) and Keith Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility: Manners and Civilisation in Early Modern England*, (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2018).

¹¹ Barry, ‘Introduction’, 9-10.

¹² Keith Wrightson, *English Society 1580-1680* (London: Routledge 1982), 2-8.

¹³ Barry et. al, *The Middling Sort of People*.

Most importantly, the diverse study of textiles and clothing works in conjunction with related efforts to study the social order. Economic histories such as those by Lorna Weatherill, Keith Wrightson, and Joan Thirsk have had limited scopes as they investigate clothing and textiles to demonstrate changing patterns of consumption and the emergence of a consumer society within early modern England in the late seventeenth century.¹⁴ Few attempts have been made to understand the social role of clothing in early modern England and those that have, prioritised elite clothing culture.¹⁵ A significant body of work has also emerged in recent years concerning sartorial politics, exploring the role of early modern clothing in the enforcement of royal and courtly identities.¹⁶ Nonetheless, while much of this research is solely applicable to the upper gentry and the aristocracy, certain findings, particularly the notion of clothing being used as a tool of social distinction, can be translated to a study of the social historian's middling sort. Danae Tankard has completed a comprehensive study on seventeenth-century clothing in provincial England. Using a series of case studies from Sussex, she succinctly summarises what was worn in the countryside, how they accessed these goods locally and through commerce with London, as well as the multitude of ways in which clothing was conceived as governing social, gender, and age identities.¹⁷ However, while her work addresses, in part, the middling sort, her primary examples concentrate on members of the rural gentry who possessed the financial resources to travel to London or shop via proxy for current fashions.¹⁸ Regardless, this

¹⁴ Joan Thirsk, *Economic Policy and Projects: The Development of a Consumer Society in Early Modern England* (Oxford: Oxford University Press 1978), Lorna Weatherill, *Consumer Behaviour & Material Culture in Britain 1660-1760*, Second Edition (London: Routledge 1996), and Keith Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities: Economic Lives in Early Modern Britain, 1470-1750* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000).

¹⁵ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite* and Vincent, "When I am in Good Habit".

¹⁶ See for example, Maria Hayward, *Stuart Style: Monarchy, Dress and the Scottish Male Elite* (London; New Haven: Yale University Press, 2020) and Erin Griffey, *Sartorial Politics in Early Modern Europe: Fashioning Women* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2019).

¹⁷ Danae Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England* (London: Bloomsbury Visual Arts 2020), 1-17.

¹⁸ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 65, 74-83

literature presents compelling evidence that suggests the advantages of exploring the social and cultural role of clothing in early modern England beyond an elite level.

A growing number of publications explore the lowest orders of society and the proliferation of fashion to the labouring poor.¹⁹ Of note in this scholarship are the works of Margaret Spufford and Susan Mee, both of whom have published extensively on the subject- they mainly specialise on the diverse impecunious population of rural England.²⁰ Unfortunately, few of these monographs consider the middling sort, with wide-ranging incomes and varying access to material goods. Nevertheless, by combining these distinct trends of historiography with pioneering work on sumptuary legislation such as that of Francis Baldwin and Wilfrid Hooper and their successors, N.B Harte and Alan Hunt, one can piece together the complex puzzle of early modern clothing. They can then ascertain its undeniable importance in governing social relations and creating and challenging unique communal identities.²¹ Ultimately, it is evident that the study of clothing can effectively contribute to the broader study of history.

¹⁹ Steven King and Christina Payne, 'The Dress of the Poor', *Textile History* 22 (2002), 1-8.

²⁰ Margaret Spufford, *The Great Reclothing of Rural England* (London: Hambledon Press, 1994), Margaret Spufford and Susan Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort: 1570-1700* (New York: OUP Oxford, 2017).

²¹ Frances Baldwin, *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation in England* (Baltimore 1923), Wilfrid Hooper, 'The Tudor Sumptuary Laws', *The English Historical Review* 30 (1915), Alan Hunt, *Governance of the Consuming Passions, A History of Sumptuary Law* (London: Palgrave 1996), and N.B. Harte, 'State Control of Dress and Social Change in Pre-Industrial England', in, *Trade, Government and Economy in Pre-Industrial England*,(eds.) D.C. Coleman & A.H. John (London, 1976), 132-65.

Order and Obedience in Early Modern English Society

Contemporary attitudes towards the social order should be considered. Sermons such as the 1547 *Homily on Obedience* stressed that God had structured the world in ‘a most excellent and perfect order’, and failure to adhere to one’s preordained social position could only result in discord and the breakdown of society.²² This ‘Great Chain of Being’ drew from medieval precedents of cosmic order and Christian morality to create a ladder or chain beginning with inanimate objects, through plants, animals, man, and ultimately angels.²³ In an effort to maintain order during periods of increased social mobility, elites sought to create a unique culture that would distance them from the middling sort.²⁴ They accomplished this in part through the publication of conduct books and treatises, such as Sir Thomas Elyot’s *Boke Named the Governour*, which outlined the education and pedigree required for any productive member of society or member of state, and emphasised that ‘without order may be nothing stable or permanent’.²⁵

Similarly, polite manners became a sign of deference, forcing people to behave according to their respective position within society.²⁶ Gestural codes were equally important as physical signs of courtesy, many of which involved articles of clothing such as docking one’s hat to a social superior.²⁷ This confirms that dress was an unmistakable symbol of status and respect, that could be used as a tool in enforcing order. However, equally important to the contextualisation of social relations in early modern England is the growing mobility of the

²² Thomas Cranmer, ‘The Homily on Obedience’, *First Book of Homilies* (1547), 105.

²³ Tillyard, *The Elizabethan World Picture*, 7, 35-6 and Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities*, 27.

²⁴ Barry, ‘Introduction’, 24.

²⁵ Sir Thomas Elyot, *The Boke named the Governour* (1531) 4-5.

²⁶ Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility*, 19, 68.

²⁷ Walter, ‘Gesturing at Authority’, 120.

middling sort and the ‘permeable membrane’ that granted those with means access into the ranks of the lower gentry.²⁸ While contemporaries sought to segregate society into categories or estates, in reality, this was significantly complicated by the lofty aspirations of many yeomen and professionals, along with an accumulation of wealth in the sixteenth century that made their ascent possible.²⁹ Therefore, in addition to their behaviours, the gentry turned to clothing as a means of separating themselves from their social inferiors.

Early modern textiles and material culture also require contextualisation to draw a distinct parallel to the changing social relations described above. Clothing was closely linked to decorum and appropriate behaviour as well as a civilised identity.³⁰ While theorists and historians often attribute the emergence of conspicuous consumption to the nineteenth-century bourgeoisie, its origins can be traced back to the beginnings of a consumer culture in the early modern period.³¹ Although some cite the years following the Civil War (1642-1651) as the initial roots of fashionable imitation, evidence suggests that emulation predated the expansion of the consumer market and was indicative of a shift in social morality.³² The growing prosperity of yeomen farmers in the sixteenth century contributed to the ‘erosion’ of the old economic order seen through a growing pattern of social mobility and increased spending as well as social emulation.³³ For most households, besides food, clothing constituted the most substantial annual expenditure, signifying its innate importance.³⁴ Greater accessibility to material goods, both domestic and imported, led to an increasing number of popular styles, and

²⁸ Wrightson, *English Society*, 8.

²⁹ Wrightson, *English Society*, 4-6.

³⁰ Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility*, 19.

³¹ Sara Pennell, ‘Consumption and Consumerism in Early Modern England’, *The Historical Journal* 42 (1999), 558.

³² Barry, ‘Introduction’, 19.

³³ Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities*, 3-7.

³⁴ Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 4 and Weatherill, *Consumer Behavior*, 119.

the rapid evolution of fashion.³⁵ This culminated in the increased importance of clothing to ‘reveal or conceal social position’.³⁶

The Proliferation of Fashionable Ideals Across England and its Consequences

The nationwide increase in consumption significantly impacted the clothing worn by the wealthy, the poor, and the middling sort across urban environments and the countryside, in both similar and disparate ways. London was the capital of fashion, and residents relied on apparel for public social display, where it could be recognised, acknowledged and replicated.³⁷ Due to its centre for international trade and fabric importation, urban fashion tended to be more colourful and varied, and members of the middling sort had better access to domestic and imported goods than their rural counterparts.³⁸ In contrast, practicality often dictated the styles in the rural areas, despite the desire of many country inhabitants. For many members of the country gentry, they could shop in London for fashionable styles either in person, or through the use of a proxy.³⁹ However, this did not prevent the middling sort, located outside the cities, from dressing fashionably as probate inventories reported an increase in the quantity and quality of clothing owned by yeomen in comparison to their less affluent neighbours.⁴⁰ Regardless of the region, clothing symbolised social status and connections, intended for a public demonstration of wealth and identity.⁴¹ Rural residents also benefited from the diffusion of urban goods to the countryside, often in the hands of petty chapmen or travelling merchants,

³⁵ N.B. Harte, ‘The Economics of Clothing in the Late Seventeenth Century’, *Textile History* 22 (1991), 278 and Thirsk, *Economic Policy and Projects*, 14-15.

³⁶ Weatherill, *Consumer Behavior*, 9 and Roche, *The Culture of Clothing*, 4.

³⁷ Breward *The Culture of Fashion*, 50-52.

³⁸ Maria Anne Hayward, *Rich apparel: clothing and the law in Henry VII's England* (London: Ashgate, 2009), 332.

³⁹ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 82-83.

⁴⁰ Anne Buck, ‘Clothing and Textiles in Bedfordshire Inventories, 1617-1620’, *Costume* 34 (2000), 29.

⁴¹ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 332.

who carried cloth, trims, and haberdashery material to small villages.⁴² Local mercers are also possessed a considerable amount of material and ready-made goods, particularly by the latter portion of the seventeenth century.⁴³ Margaret Spufford conducted extensive research on the importance of petty chapmen in the distribution of textiles across the country. They were especially known for the sale of decoration and embellishment used to reflect status and wealth as well as accessible ready-made clothing and accessories.⁴⁴ With their suppliers located in London, chapmen, many of whom later established market stalls or storefronts, provided an essential connection between urban fashion and the countryside- thus, they minimised some of the fundamental disparities in wealth and style.⁴⁵ It is evident that members of the urban and rural middling sort, including yeomen farmers, shop-keepers, and professionals, all experienced a degree of economic prosperity that enabled them to invest in the growing number of fashionable styles and to cultivate their image in a manner that those socially beneath them could not.⁴⁶

⁴² Weatherill, *Consumer Behaviour*, 90 and Spufford, *The Great Reclathing*, 51-52.

⁴³ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 58-69.

⁴⁴ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 119 and Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, xvi.

⁴⁵ Spufford, *The Great Reclathing*, 58, 78.

⁴⁶ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 327-328.

Identity, Morality, and Clothing in a Contemporary Context

Due to the proliferation of fashion across the country, distinct perceptions towards apparel became deeply entrenched in the enforcement of the social order, driving scholars to assess the impact of clothing and dress on contemporary attitudes.⁴⁷ In addition to describing the appropriate manners for behaving at court and at home, conduct books were instrumental in enforcing the importance of clothing as a social tool linked to decorum and status.⁴⁸ They dictated the origins of modern conceptions of the self and the importance of appearance as a display of inner character.⁴⁹ One of the most influential conduct books in England and abroad was Baldassare Castiglione's *The Courtier*. Hoby's English 1561 translation proved to be a seminal work in connecting apparel to the broader formation of an elite cultural identity. Castiglione argued that a man 'ought to determine with himselfe what he will appeere to be, and in suche sorte as he desireth to bee esteamed so to appaile himselfe, and make his garmentes helpe him to be counted suche a one.'⁵⁰ Over a century later, Sir Francis Osborne stressed a similar sentiment in his 1656 *Advice to a Son*, arguing that one should 'wear your clothes neat, exceeding rather than coming short of others of like fortune.'⁵¹ Increasing rates of literacy meant that the advice incorporated in these conduct books could also be appropriated by aspirational members of the middling sort. Conduct books encouraged individuals to 'appear what he was, but also what he aspired to be', and as such, by propagating fashionable styles through these publications, the middling sort were able to more effectively emulate and blend in with the gentry and the classes above.⁵² Both sources highlight the importance of apparel for

⁴⁷ Elias, *The Civilizing Process*, 61-63.

⁴⁸ Thomas, *In Pursuit of Civility*, 66.

⁴⁹ Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self*, 155-157

⁵⁰ Baldissare Castiglione, *The Book of the Courtier trans. by Sir Thomas Hoby*, (ed.) Sir Walter Raleigh (London: Davis Nutt Publisher, 1900), accessed December 7, 2021, <http://www.luminarium.org/renascence-editions/courtier/courtier2.html>.

⁵¹ Francis Osborne, *Advice to a Son* (London 1656), 12.

⁵² Osborne, *Advice to a Son*, 55.

elite members of society to distinguish themselves as socially superior linkable to Elias's Civilizing Process, as well as Veblen's hypothesis on the importance of conspicuous consumption by further associating good manners and an influence on dress selection.⁵³

Morality similarly played a fundamental role in defining attitudes towards clothing in the early modern period.⁵⁴ Excesses in dress were considered both a personal and a public vice.⁵⁵ Sermons and prescriptive literature of the era relayed the dangers of dressing above one's station, despite acknowledging the impact of clothing on the delineation of social order.⁵⁶ Superficial and impractical decorations, such as ruffs, were indicative of one's status, but were often a source of ridicule by moralists, particularly Puritans.⁵⁷ Bishop John Jewel's 1571 *Homily Against Excesses of Apparel* was widely circulated and read aloud in churches throughout the country. Jewel reiterated the God-given place of each man within society and condemned those who dressed in apparel unbecoming for their social level.⁵⁸ A similar sentiment was expressed by Samuel Annesley in 1671 when he plead 'That yet there are some modes of Apparel... so inconsistent with the Rule of Decency, so apparently transgressing the bounds of Modesty, that no pretence of an honest intention, no uprightness of heart can atone, or excuse the evil of wearing them.'⁵⁹ In addition to sermons, contemporary publications, often authored by members of the gentry, also signalled concern for the excesses of apparel, such as Richard Allestree's *The Whole Duty of Man*, which states that the 'end of apparel is the distinguishing

⁵³ Roche, *The Culture of Clothing*, 54-55.

⁵⁴ Breward, *The Culture of Fashion*, 50.

⁵⁵ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 46.

⁵⁶ Catherine Richardson, 'Introduction' in, *Clothing Culture, 1350-1650*, ed. Catherine Richardson (Aldershot: Routledge, 2004), 1.

⁵⁷ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 32-33, 86.

⁵⁸ Bishop John Jewel, 'Homily Against Excess of Apparel', *Second Book of Homilies* (1571), accessed December 7, 2021, <http://www.anglicanlibrary.org/homilies/bk2hom06.htm>.

⁵⁹ Samuel Annesley, *A Continuation of morning-exercise questions and cases of conscience practically resolved by sundry ministers in October, 1682* (London 1683), 608.

and differencing of persons'.⁶⁰ Essentially, these publications were not only critiquing the extravagance of contemporary attire, but confirming that clothing distinguished various ranks, and those who dressed above their status were disrupting the divine Great Chain of Being.

In addition to conducting books and sermons, other forms of prescriptive literature articulated contemporary anxieties regarding excesses in apparel. Philip Stubbes' 1583 *An Anatomie of Abuses* can be regarded as a pivotal work in moralising literature that fuses secular and religious discourse, to target apparel specifically.⁶¹ Stubbes provided an exceptionally thorough evaluation of contemporary clothing, and comments how individuals of all social ranks 'go daily in silks, velvets, satins, damasks, taffetas, and such like, notwithstanding that they be both base by birth, mean by estate, and calling.'⁶² He further describes the clothing worn by members of society, decrying the ornate fabrics and colours used in the everyday clothing of the common sort, and lambasting their frivolous styles such as overly decorated hats.⁶³ Although Stubbes and many of his fellow writers could be characterised as overtly biased, even extremist due to his puritanical views, his writings are indicative of the mindset wherein apparel was identified as a potent social tool.⁶⁴ This moral argument against current fashionability may have been used to disguise their ulterior motive- to prevent people from emulating gentlemanly styles and enforce social stratification. In addition to unveiling the undeniable connection between apparel and the enforcement of social order, the frequency of these publications reflects the regularity of such offences, and an increasing concern amongst the elite regarding these overt displays.

⁶⁰ Richard Allestree, *The Whole Duty of Man* (1659), 238-239.

⁶¹ Roze Hentschell, 'Moralizing Apparel in Early Modern London: Popular Literature, Sermons, and Sartorial Display', *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies* 39 (2009): 575.

⁶² Phillip Stubbes, *An Anatomie of Abuses* (1583), accessed December 7, 2021, <https://ezp.lib.cam.ac.uk/login?url=https://www-proquest-com.ezp.lib.cam.ac.uk/books/front-matter-stage-plays-enterluds-etc/docview/2138578574/se-2?accountid=9851>.

⁶³ Stubbes, *An Anatomie of Abuses* (1583).

⁶⁴ Vincent, "When I am in Good Habit", 118.

Beyond Morality: Sumptuary Legislation and the Enforcement of the Social Order

It is equally noteworthy that the government focused on the enforcement of the Great Chain of Being through the implementation of sumptuary legislation that enshrined into law the relationship between clothing and the social order. The Henrician Acts of Apparel, passed in 1533, along with a subsequent Act passed by Queen Elizabeth I in 1553, proved to be the most comprehensive and enduring.⁶⁵ Elizabeth seemed particularly preoccupied with the enforcement of sumptuary law. She issued nineteen additional proclamations on the subject of dress between 1562 and 1597, to deal with wide-ranging topics from the ‘the outrageous double ruffs which now of late are crept in’ to prescriptive legislation encouraging yeomen farmers and husbandmen to wear felt caps as part of their daily apparel.⁶⁶ Francis Baldwin and Wilfrid Hooper, the preeminent scholars on England sumptuary law, derived three basic principles from this legislation- to preserve the domestic economy and limit the importation of foreign goods, to condemn and prevent excessive luxury, and most importantly, to preserve class structures.⁶⁷ Sumptuary legislation ensured that one’s social position could easily be ascertained, and its success or failure demonstrated the inherent value being placed on clothing.⁶⁸ It also served to control the spending of the lower orders to avoid and prevent them from slipping into poverty or crime to support their extravagant taste. This was evidenced by Elizabeth’s dramatic 1574 proclamation in which she decried ‘the ruin of a multitude of serviceable young men and gentlemen and of many good families’ through their excesses in apparel.⁶⁹ Generally, sumptuary legislation targeted young men, and it was enforced particularly strenuously amongst

⁶⁵ Baldwin, *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation*, 267 and Harte, ‘State Control of Dress’, 135.

⁶⁶ Harte, ‘State Control of Dress’, 135, Proclamation 7 May 1562, 4 Eliz. I (495).

⁶⁷ Baldwin, *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation*, 2 and Hooper, ‘The Tudor Sumptuary Laws’, 436.

⁶⁸ Joanne Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self* (Philadelphia: Polity Press, 1991), 137-139.

⁶⁹ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 18 and Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601).

those attending university, many of whom grazed the social divide between the gentry and middling sort.⁷⁰ This exemplifies how elite anxieties regarding apparel were codified into law to restrict socially mobile young men and to reaffirm traditional ideas of the social order.

The very structure and wording of sumptuary legislation and subsequent proclamations validates the crown's primary motivation of maintaining and enforcing patterns of social order. The preamble to Henry VIII's 1533 Act of Apparel explicitly details how excesses in apparel led to the 'undoing of many in expert and light persons inclined to pride mother of all vices and 'the subversion of good and politic order in knowledge and distinction of people according to their estates, pre-eminences dignities and degrees'.⁷¹ This perfectly illustrates a dual motivation for implementing control over the apparel of the lower orders- it serves to preserve their morality, but more importantly to establish boundaries ensuring that individuals can be easily distinguished based on their appearance. Queen Elizabeth expresses a similar sentiment in her proclamations against Excesses of Apparel, stating that over time there had been 'the disorder and confusion of the degrees of all estates (wherein always diversity of apparel hath taken place)' as well as condemning 'the wasting and undoing of a great number of young gentlemen... seeking by show of apparel to be esteemed as gentlemen'.⁷² These statements provide vital support for early modern applications of Veblen by explicitly describing how young men leveraged conspicuous consumption to emulate their social superiors.⁷³ Though emulative consumption was regarded as an urban fear, it clearly served as a means of marking societal division.⁷⁴ The concerns expressed by religious moralists echo the Queen's messaging to demonstrate throughout the sixteenth century- there were shared anxieties regarding the

⁷⁰ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 131-132.

⁷¹ 24 Hen. VIII, 13 (1533).

⁷² Proclamation 12 February 1566, 8 Eliz. I (542) and Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601).

⁷³ Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self*, 140.

⁷⁴ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 34-35.

enhanced access to apparel that led both civic and moral-minded officials to take a firmer stand to preserve order within the nation.

Additionally, the details of the legislation itself are critical of the argument of its use to enforce social order within English society. In general, it was not the styles of clothing that differed between members of the middling sort and the elites, but rather the colour, fabric, and level of ornamentation that were regulated. For example, metallic fabric, velvet and silk embroidery were all restricted to those in the gentry and above as well as a number of restrictions on fur trimmings.⁷⁵ These guidelines were outlined in sumptuary legislation throughout social levels or conditions and grew increasingly detailed as new legislation was passed. Typically, a monarch and his or her family were granted the most significant liberties, followed closely by members of the court and the landed gentry, then freeholding yeomen farmers, and finally husbandmen and labourers.⁷⁶ Within these categories, there were more granular distinctions, often based upon titles, landholdings, and accumulated wealth. Amongst the gentry, the common gentleman had the fewest options in apparel, thus encouraging ‘unscrupulous’ individuals to pass themselves off as members of the gentry.⁷⁷ At times, there was little difference in the restrictions placed upon members of the lesser gentry and wealthy members of the middling sort, making it even more essential for the gentry to distinguish themselves from their social inferiors.⁷⁸ Evidently, though sumptuary legislation served a multitude of purposes, it was above all an invaluable weapon of the crown to dictate the degrees of society.

⁷⁵ Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601).

⁷⁶ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 204-210.

⁷⁷ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 210.

⁷⁸ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 221.

By 1604, sumptuary legislation had been repealed, and subsequent attempts by James I and Charles I to reinstate it failed to pass through the House of Commons.⁷⁹ The early disappearance of sumptuary legislation in England, as compared to continental Europe, puzzles historians such as N.B Harte, who has confessed his inability to provide a sufficient explanation.⁸⁰ Alan Hunt has proposed a number of alternative explanations in his nuanced approach to the study of sumptuary legislation, but has reiterated the general uncertainty within the scholarship.⁸¹ He theorised that the absence of seventeenth-century legislation to control apparel might reflect the rapidly changing styles of the early modern period. After the passing of the Henrician sumptuary legislation in 1533, men's style transitioned from long gowns to the doublet and hose, and eventually to the suit by the end of the seventeenth century.⁸² Additionally, the commercial regulation made it impossible for legislation to keep up with increasingly diverse styles.⁸³ Similarly, while sumptuary legislation mandated what was desirable, it did little to prevent people from purchasing forbidden fabrics and was virtually impossible to be enforced, therefore implying what was desirable, but doing little to prevent its acquisition.⁸⁴ Despite placing guards at the entrance to London during Queen Elizabeth's reign, it became increasingly apparent that in order for sumptuary legislation to be effectively upheld, the people needed to report and self-regulate excesses within their community- this proved to be unpopular.⁸⁵ In her final proclamation on the subject of apparel, Elizabeth lamented how 'no reformation at all hath followed' her previous declarations, indicating that sumptuary legislation was clearly being

⁷⁹ Harte, 'State Control of Dress', 134 and Maria Hayward, "'Outlandish Superfluities': Luxury and Clothing in Scottish and English Sumptuary Law from the Fourteenth to the Seventeenth Century', *The Right to Dress: Sumptuary Laws in a Global Perspective, c.1200–1800*, eds. Giorgio Riello and Ulinka Rublack (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019), 97.

⁸⁰ Harte, 'State Control of Dress', 153-154.

⁸¹ Hunt, *Governance of the Consuming Passions*, 357-361.

⁸² Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 115.

⁸³ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 336.

⁸⁴ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 84, 108.

⁸⁵ Hooper, 'The Tudor Sumptuary Laws', 439-443.

ignored.⁸⁶ Ultimately, despite Elizabeth's 'Herculean' efforts to enforce these laws, their existence failed to stem the tide of change, nor to blur the boundaries between the gentry and the middling sort.⁸⁷

Fashioning the Middling Sort

The desire of the elite within English society to restrict apparel across all social levels was aided by the financial constraints of the middling sort. However, despite most attempts from the church, state, and community to regulate the clothing worn by this group, these efforts failed. In instances where the middling sort were unable to afford to dress in the apparel of their social superiors, they found inexpensive alternatives such as *mockado*, a fake velvet that is commonly found among upper-middling sort inventories. These substitutions generally left them with the necessary resources to invest in higher quality textiles and ornamentation, as opposed to basic russet or linen worn by husbandmen or more impoverished artisans.⁸⁸ The great care the middling sort afforded to their clothing also serves as an indication of the inherent value it held.⁸⁹ Therefore, it can be argued that despite the apparent differences in the overall quality of the apparel of the gentry and middling sort, clothing was essential for grooming people for the role they sought to inhabit as well as the role they were expected to inhabit.⁹⁰ Similarly, as traditional community values eroded and cities increased in size, urban anonymity made it increasingly possible for the middling sort to masquerade above their social position without recognition, and for members to invest in clothing specifically designed to attract the

⁸⁶ Proclamation 6 July 1597, 39 Eliz. I (786).

⁸⁷ Harte, 'State control of Dress', 148.

⁸⁸ Spufford and Mee, *Clothing of the Common Sort*, 132, 217.

⁸⁹ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 133.

⁹⁰ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 177.

community's attention.⁹¹ Again, this emphasises a profound early modern anxiety regarding the disguise and manipulation of appearance which directly challenged the Great Chain of Being.⁹² It is equally evident that by establishing parameters and guidance, the conduct books, sermons, and sumptuary legislation were setting precedents for what could be worn. In fact, this determined what was in style and accordingly increased the demand for such prohibitive fashions.⁹³ Therefore, rather than suppressing attire, the conduct books, sermons, and sumptuary legislation encouraged styles to spread further and promoted the desire to own such prohibited goods.⁹⁴ In other instances, like the case of caps, this notoriety would cause items to fall out of fashion quickly, as they became the prescriptive headwear or garments for yeomen, husbandmen, and below.⁹⁵ Therefore, the very actions taken to create distinct social boundaries ultimately contributed to the crossover between the gentry and the literate, as aspirational members of the middling sort made fashion the 'joint expression of status aspiration and status assertion'.⁹⁶

The inability of the gentry to successfully define their 'class' identity through clothing correlates to the distinction of societal expectations versus fundamental reality. This principle has its foundation in the work of James C. Scott, who describes a 'hidden transcript' that contrasts acceptable public belief, and argues that in truth there is a distinct difference between expected behaviour and what is actually practised.⁹⁷ Although the gentry assumed an elevated level of social ranking, it is increasingly evident that such roles were flexible within society. As

⁹¹ Pennell, 'Consumption and Consumerism', 550 and Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 164.

⁹² Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 10.

⁹³ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 127.

⁹⁴ Breward, *The Culture of Fashion*, 55.

⁹⁵ Hayward, *Rich apparel*, 25.

⁹⁶ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 127.

⁹⁷ James C. Scott, *Domination and the Arts of Resistance, Hidden Transcripts*, (London: Yale University Press, 1990, 1-15.

noted above, the transformation within both urban and rural communities led to a reevaluation of how the middling sort regarded themselves and articulated their status. Specifically, their acquisition of clothing signified the increasing wealth and social aspirations of the middling sort, contradicting traditional orders dictating that people must stay within their respective estates.⁹⁸ Nevertheless, even those beneath the middling sort were able to engage in the culture of fashion from the middle of the sixteenth century onwards. A rapidly expanding market in second-hand and stolen clothing as well as inexpensive, ready-made accessories and apparel confirm that clothing was an important tool of social elevation and emulation.⁹⁹ Chapmen also offered goods at a variety of prices so that everyone could find fashionable clothing at an appropriate level.¹⁰⁰ However, this reality was not expressed in the sumptuary legislation, conduct books, and prescriptive literature that placed a significant emphasis on the separation of society into different groups and the necessity of a separation between the lower gentry and aspirational middling sort. While these sources promoted an idealised version of society, or a public transcript, they ignored the hidden reality wherein social mobility was a contemporary phenomenon, and these documents were appropriated by those seeking to emulate elite customs and fashion and to break down the traditional social order. Therefore, it is apparent that even if the gentry sought to use fashion to create a unique identity for themselves, their failure to consider the larger machinations of early modern society largely contributed to the undoing of their own sartorial uniformity. Instead, it allowed the middling sort to fashion a cultural identity of their own.

Conclusion

⁹⁸ Vincent, ‘When I am in Good Habit’, 20.

⁹⁹ Beverly Lemire, ‘The Theft of Clothes and Popular Consumerism in Early Modern England’, *Journal of Social History* 24 (1990): 255, 269 and Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 40-41.

¹⁰⁰ Thirsk, *Economic Policy and Projects*, 116.

Although it was initially intended to be another mechanism for enforcing the social order, apparel ultimately delivered the opposite effect as it created a sense of ambiguity between social classes. Beginning in the sixteenth century, fashion became 'a means for publicising social status', with increased mobility and purchasing power fostering such dramatic change.¹⁰¹ Despite the fact that the incomes of the middling sort varied dramatically, much of their finances were devoted to fashionable textiles and apparel, portraying their growing influence in society and infringement on the positions of the landed gentry.¹⁰² While there has been limited historiographical research dedicated to assessing the impact of clothing on social relations in early modern England, this survey has demonstrated that by expanding the analysis to increasingly diverse historiography, there is compelling evidence to support the fundamental theory of emulation proposed by Veblen at the turn of the twentieth century. This challenges criticism of emulation theory which postulates that the middling sort created a distinctive identity through fashion separate from the gentry, and perhaps even influenced courtly attire.¹⁰³

As noted at the beginning of this article, despite a general increase in scholarship on the subject of dress, a survey of relevant literature revealed that the study of clothing within the broader field of social history was lacking. This provided a historiographical foundation and methodological framework for the arguments presented while acknowledging the gaps in the literature. Secondly, contemporary ideals regarding the social order, deference, and the 'great chain of being' were summarised, followed by a brief investigation of how fashion and cultural trends could circulate throughout early modern England. These studies support the argument that the study of dress and textiles fits into contemporary understanding of social order and that

¹⁰¹ Finkelstein, *The Fashioned Self*, 155-157, 165.

¹⁰² Weatherill, *Consumer Behavior*, 98-103.

¹⁰³ Wrightson, *Earthly Necessities*, 299-300.

members of the middling sort had access to clothing which effectively allowed them to emulate the gentry, even outside of urban centres. Contemporary sermons and conduct books were studied in great detail. This exposed the moral impetus to restrict dress to preserve social order and prevent excessive consumption while simultaneously advancing the view that apparel was a crucial tool in defining their own identity as gentlemen. Likewise, an exploration into the role of sumptuary legislation and contemporary ‘acts of apparel’ revealed that restricting the dress of the middling sort was not solely the preoccupation of the gentry and religious moralists but was also the subject of national governance, proving that dress was perceived as a critical tool of social identification. However, the failure of these sumptuary laws was equally telling, indicating that despite the best efforts of elite society, there was little they could do to control dress and its use by the middling sort. Finally, the ‘hidden transcript’ of the middling sort was uncovered, demonstrating that despite the best efforts of elite society, individuals were able to ingeniously replicate the fashions of their social betters, despite financial constraints. This ultimately demonstrates that rather than restricting dress, sumptuary legislation, conduct books, and sermons on apparel effectively provided insight into what was fashionable, encouraging emulation by the middling sort, rather than curtailing it. By connecting these arguments, it becomes apparent that clothing was perceived as a potent tool across contemporary society in constructing social and cultural identities. By exploring the variety of ways in which these ideas could be articulated across early modern English society, one can observe how despite the best efforts of the gentry, the middling sort were able to wield clothing as a weapon for social advancement.

Contemporary evidence suggests that while the middling sort were frequently the arbiters of fashion, they often considered this role in response to the economic, legal, and moral limitations placed upon them by the gentry. Perhaps, while seeking to emulate the culture of the elite, the

middling sort ultimately devised a culture of their own.¹⁰⁴ Alternatively, as Danae Tankard argues, emulative consumption was not vertical, but instead based around the desire of both the rural gentry and middling sort to mimic fashionable apparel from the urban centre of London.¹⁰⁵ Regardless, to early modern observers, fashion enabled social recognition, and thus, was an integral tool in the construction of social groups and the maintenance of order.¹⁰⁶ In subverting the existing boundaries of fashion and appearance, the middling sort established a fundamental role in restructuring English society that continues to impact the evolving field of social history today.

¹⁰⁴ Spufford and Mee, *The Clothing of the Common Sort*, 220-221.

¹⁰⁵ Tankard, *Clothing in 17th-Century Provincial England*, 185

¹⁰⁶ Vincent, *Dressing the Elite*, 92.

Bibliography

Primary Sources

Acts and Proclamations of Apparel, Archival

24 Hen.VIII, 13 (1533)

Proclamation 7 May 1562, 4 Eliz. I (495)

Proclamation 12 February 1566, 8 Eliz. I (542)

Proclamation 15 June 1574, 16 Eliz. I (601)

Proclamation 6 July 1597, 39 Eliz. I (786)

Printed Primary Material

Allestree, Richard. *The Whole Duty of Man*. London, 1659.

Annesley, Samuel. *A Continuation of morning-exercise questions and cases of conscience practicaly resolved by sundry ministers in October, 1682*. London, 1683.

Castiglione, Baldissare. *The Book of the Courtier* trans. by Sir Thomas Hoby, (ed.) Sir Walter Raleigh (London: Davis Nutt Publisher, 1900), accessed December 7, 2021, <http://www.luminarium.org/renascence-editions/courtier/courtier2.html>.

Cranmer, Thomas. 'The Homily on Obedience', *First Book of Homilies*, 1547.

Elyot, Sir Thomas. *The Boke named the Governour*. London, 1531.

Jewel, Bishop John. 'Homily Against Excess of Apparel', *Second book of Homilies*, 1571, accessed December 7, 2021, <http://www.anglicanlibrary.org/homilies/bk2hom06.htm>.

Osborne, Francis. *Advice to a Son*, 1658.

Stubbes, Phillip. *An Anatomy of Abuses*. London, 1583, accessed December 7, 2021, <https://ezp.lib.cam.ac.uk/login?url=https://www-proquest-com.ezp.lib.cam.ac.uk/books/front-matter-stage-playes-enterluds-etc/docview/2138578574/se-2?accountid=9851>.

Secondary Sources

- Allen, D.E. 'Fashion as a Social Process', *Textile History* 22 (1991): 347-358.
- Baldwin, Frances. *Sumptuary Legislation and Personal Regulation in England*. Baltimore, 19.
- Barry, Jonathan and Brooks, Christopher, eds. *The Middling Sort of People: Culture, Society, and Politics in England, 1550-1800*. London: Palgrave, 1994.
- Beward, Christopher, *The Culture of Fashion*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1995.
- Buck, Anne. 'Clothing and Textiles in Bedfordshire Inventories, 1617-1620', *Costume* 34 (2000): 25-38.
- Coleman D.C. and John, A.H. (eds.). *Trade, Government and Economy in Pre-Industrial England*. London, 1976.
- Crane, Diana. *Fashion and its Social Agendas: Class, Gender and Identity in Clothing*. London: University of Chicago Press, 2000.
- Elias, Norbert. *The Civilizing Process*. London: Wiley-Blackwell, 2000.
- Finkelstein, Joanne. *The Fashioned Self*. Philadelphia: Polity Press, 1991.
- Griffey, Erin, *Sartorial Politics in Early Modern Europe: Fashioning Women*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2019.
- Harte, N.B, 'The Economics of Clothing in the Late Seventeenth Century', *Textile History* 22 (1991): 275-289.
- Hayward, Maria Anne. *Rich apparel: clothing and the law in Henry VII's England*. London: Ashgate, 2009.
- Hayward, Maria. *Stuart Style: Monarchy, Dress and the Scottish Male Elite*. London: New Haven: Yale University Press, 2020
- Hentschell, Roze. 'Moralizing Apparel in Early Modern London: Popular Literature, Sermons, and Sartorial Display', *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies* 39 (2009): 571-595.
- Hooper, Wilfrid. 'The Tudor Sumptuary Laws', *the English Historical Review* 30 (1915).
- Hunt, Alan. *Governance of the Consuming Passions, A History of Sumptuary Law*. London: Palgrave, 1996.
- King, Steven and Payne, Christina. 'The Dress of the Poor', *Textile History* (2002): 1-8.
- Lemire, Beverly. 'The Theft of Clothes and Popular Consumerism in Early Modern England', *Journal of Social History* 24 (1990): 255-276.

- Pennell, Sara. 'Consumption and Consumerism in Early Modern England', *The Historical Journal* 42 (1999),: 549-564.
- Richardson, Catherine (ed.), *Clothing Culture, 1350-1650*. London: Aldershot, 2004.
- Riello, Giorgio and Rublack, Ulinka, eds. *The Right to Dress: Sumptuary Laws in a Global Perspective, c.1200–1800*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- Roche, Daniel. *The Culture of Clothing: Dress and Fashion in the Ancien Regime* trans. by Jean Birrell. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996.
- Spufford, Margaret. *The Great Reclotting of Rural England*. London: Hambledon Press, 1994.
- Spufford, Margaret and Mee, Susan. *The Clothing of the Common Sort: 1570-1700*. New York: OUP Oxford, 2017.
- Tillyard, E.M.W. *The Elizabethan World Picture*. London: 1943.
- Thirsk, Joan. *Economic Policy and Projects: The Development of a Consumer Society in early Modern England*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1978.
- Thomas, Keith. *In Pursuit of Civility: Manners and Civilization in Early Modern England*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2018.
- Vincent, S. 'When I am in Good Habit': Clothes in English Culture c. 1550- c. 1670', Doctor of Philosophy Dissertation: University of York, 2002.
- Vincent, Susan. *Dressing the Elite: Clothes in Early Modern England*. Oxford: Berg, 2003.
- Walter, J. 'Gesturing at Authority: Deciphering the Gestural Code of Early Modern England', in M. Braddick, ed. *The Politics of Gesture: Historical Perspectives* (Past and Present, Supplement, 4, 2009: 100-127.
- Weatherill, Lorna. *Consumer Behaviour & Material Culture in Britain 1660-1760, Second Edition*. London: Routledge, 1996.
- Wrightson, Keith. *Earthly Necessities: Economic Lives in Early Modern Britain, 1470-1750*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 2000.
- Wrightson, Keith, *English Society 1580-1680*. London: Routledge, 1982.